

High-resolution, low-loss multilevel phase shifters based on electrically driven phase-change materials integrated onto silicon waveguides

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Abstract: Multilevel phase shifters are key components in photonic integrated circuits. A major requirement in many applications is achieving non-volatile operation and low insertion loss simultaneously. Electrically, multiple phase levels can be encoded by controlling the heater power and employing different microheater architectures to induce varying degrees of phase-change material (PCM) amorphization, thereby modulating the device's optical properties and the amplitude and phase of the propagating field. Here, we explore a platform based on the integration of a low-loss PCM, namely GeSe, sandwiched between microheaters and silicon waveguides. To achieve a large number of levels, we modify standard straight microheaters and propose a segmented heater design that breaks the heater's symmetry along the propagation direction. We numerically demonstrate under pulse-width/pulse-amplitude modulation (PWM/PAM) that multilevel phase shifts can be achieved due to non-uniform heating in the GeSe PCM layer. However, the resulting phase levels for the basic configuration are highly abrupt because the constant power dissipation along the light propagation direction, associated with a uniform cross-section, does not permit a wide range of amorphization patterns. The proposed segmented heater, whose width gradually increases in steps along the light propagation direction, allows overcoming this limitation. This configuration enables the encoding of 164 well-spaced phase levels between 0 and π (>7-bit resolution), facilitated by smoother amorphization arising from the combined effects of non-uniform heating across segments and within each segment, while maintaining an insertion loss of only 0.6 dB in the fully crystalline state (worst case).

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1. Introduction

Reconfigurable photonic integrated circuits (PICs) have emerged as key enablers for a wide range of applications, including sensing, microwave processing, co-packaged optics, and computing [1–5]. One of the main building blocks used to realize reconfigurability is the Mach–Zehnder interferometer (MZI), in which an optical path delay is introduced between the two arms by means of a phase shifter, thereby controlling the proportion of light directed to a given port [2]. For example, in coherent photonic computing architectures, information is encoded in the amplitude of optical signals, and MZI meshes acting as complex-valued optical weights are used to perform matrix–vector multiplications (MVMs) [6]. The performance of these circuits critically depends on the properties of the phase shifters, which can be broadly classified as volatile or non-volatile. Phase shifters based on thermo-optic or free-carrier electro-optic effects are volatile and therefore require continuous power to maintain their programmed state, resulting

in high static power consumption. In contrast, non-volatile phase shifters retain their programmed state without additional power, enabling energy-efficient reconfiguration. This characteristic makes non-volatile phase shifters highly attractive for large-scale programmable photonic circuits, including photonic neural networks (PNNs).

Recently, phase-change materials (PCMs) have been explored for non-volatile phase shifting in integrated photonics [7–9]. In PCM-integrated waveguides, phase shifts can be induced by exploiting the large refractive-index change associated with switching between the crystalline and amorphous states, which is approximately two and three orders of magnitude larger than the thermo-optic and free-carrier effects, respectively [9,10]. This large refractive-index modulation substantially reduces the footprint of PCM-based phase shifters compared with devices relying on electro-optic or thermo-optic effects. However, conventional PCMs such as $\text{Ge}_2\text{Sb}_2\text{Te}_5$ (GST) often suffer from high optical losses, which degrade circuit performance [11,12]. To address this issue, alternative low-loss PCMs such as Sb_2Se_3 , Sb_2S_3 , and GeSe have been explored. These materials offer high refractive-index contrast and very low optical absorption in the telecommunications C-band at 1550 nm [13–16]. In PNNs, for example, weighted connections must be implemented precisely; therefore, it is essential to realize multilevel phase shifts that can encode a wide range of weight values. Finely spaced phase levels between the fully crystalline and fully amorphous PCM states enable higher weight resolution and can therefore improve system accuracy. Multilevel phase shifting can be realized in PCM-integrated waveguides by partially amorphizing the PCM through controlled electrical or optical programming [17–20]. By modulating the degree of amorphization, intermediate refractive-index states can be obtained, yielding a continuous range of phase shifts. In electrical programming, this control is achieved by varying the energy of the programming pulses [7–9,21–23]. However, achieving uniform and well-spaced phase levels remains challenging because the amorphization process is complex and often highly non-uniform [8,10]. Considerable effort has therefore been devoted to optimizing switching by tailoring the heating geometry and pulse energy [7–9,24–26]. Various heater architectures, including doped-silicon [8,9,24], PIN-diode [7,25,26], and ITO [19] heaters, have been investigated to enable multilevel transmission and phase shifting in low-loss PCM-integrated photonic devices. Despite these efforts, only a limited number of studies [19,24,26] have demonstrated high-resolution electrical programming beyond 5 bits in low-loss PCM-based devices. Moreover, the use of resistive metal heaters positioned above the silicon core and separated by a dielectric spacer remains largely unexplored for multilevel phase shifting, primarily because of perceived limitations in heating efficiency and cooling rate. Addressing these challenges opens a promising path toward low-loss, scalable, and precise phase control in PCM-based photonic circuits.

In this work, we investigate what we believe to be a novel GeSe-based, low-loss PCM-integrated phase shifter capable of multilevel phase control using a TiN heater positioned above the PCM. Electrical programming is examined through two approaches: (1) varying the pulse duration at fixed power and (2) varying the power at a fixed pulse duration. Two heater configurations are analyzed: a conventional constant-width heater and a segmented heater whose width gradually increases along the light propagation direction. Numerical simulations show that, although the constant-width heater under pulse-width modulation (PWM) can encode multiple phase levels, the spacing between these levels is highly irregular because of non-uniform local heating within the GeSe layer combined with uniform heating along the propagation direction. In contrast, the segmented heater enables the encoding of hundreds of well-spaced phase levels through smoother amorphization of the combined GeSe segments while maintaining a low optical insertion loss of only 0.6 dB in the worst case. Although individual segments exhibit irregular amorphization, the variation in heating across segments ensures different degrees of amorphization under the same programming conditions, leading to an overall smooth phase response. These results demonstrate

that the segmented heater design is highly suitable for integration into energy-efficient coherent PNNs and, more broadly, for the next generation of programmable photonic systems [27].

2. Device structure

The cross-sectional schematic of the phase-shifter structure considered here is shown in Fig. 1(a). The central silicon region consists of the waveguide core, on top of which a SiN_x layer is deposited, followed by the GeSe phase-change-material (PCM) layer and an AlN layer that protects the GeSe film from oxidation and improves heating efficiency. A thin 10 nm SiO_2 gap between the Si core and the SiN_x layer is included to represent the effect of chemical-mechanical polishing. A TiN heater layer is positioned 500 nm above the top of the Si core to ensure efficient heating while minimizing its impact on optical propagation. The buried oxide (BOX) thickness is 800 nm, and the SiO_2 cladding thickness is 2.5 μm . Silicon slabs are placed on either side of the core at a distance of 500 nm to promote rapid heat dissipation and thus rapid cooling of the GeSe without affecting the optical characteristics. Tungsten and copper vias of 5 μm width are placed 1 μm away from the heater edge in the trench region to further enhance the cooling of the GeSe. The thickness and width of the silicon core are 0.3 μm and 0.4 μm , respectively. The GeSe, SiN_x , AlN, and TiN layers each have a width of 1.0 μm . The thicknesses of the SiN_x , GeSe, and AlN layers are denoted by t_1 , t_2 , and t_3 , respectively, while the TiN thickness is fixed at 70 nm. The thicknesses of the tungsten and copper vias are 0.8 μm and 1.69 μm , respectively. The thicknesses of the substrate and air regions are both taken as 5 μm , and the width of the SiO_2 buffer in the leftmost and rightmost regions is set to 5 μm so that the thermal boundaries do not affect the heating and cooling of the GeSe. The thermal vias are incorporated solely to enhance heat dissipation, while the electrical vias used to drive the heater are positioned before the beginning and after the end of the phase-shifter, as shown in Fig. 1(b). The heater is extended beyond the active region to ensure that these electrical vias do not influence the temperature distribution within the GeSe layer. Under these conditions, heat flow within the phase shifter is predominantly governed by the cross-sectional geometry, making a 2D thermal model a sufficiently accurate approximation.

3. Thermal simulations and phase shift modelling

The temperature distribution within the GeSe layer was simulated using Lumerical HEAT [28]. In our 2D simulations, the mesh edge lengths were set between 1 nm and 100 nm, with a triangle quality of 30 and the simulation time step is 1 ns. The initial temperature was set to an ambient value of 20°C. All boundaries, except the upper surface, were maintained at ambient temperature. Convection boundary conditions were applied at the glass–air and copper–air interfaces, with a convection coefficient of 5 $\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$ [29]. In the simulations, the thickness of the SiN_x layer (t_1) was set to 20 nm and the GeSe thickness (t_2) was chosen as 35 nm. The thickness of the AlN layer (t_3) was set to 435 nm, filling the entire gap between the GeSe layer and the heater layer, thereby enhancing both the heating efficiency and the cooling rate because of its higher thermal conductivity compared with SiO_2 . For the proposed configurations, a phase shift of π is obtained for a phase-shifter length of 85.5 μm . Heating is induced by a low-stress TiN heater with a power density of 7.5 $\text{mW}/\mu\text{m}$ and a pulse duration of 1 μs . The corresponding electrical input can be readily estimated from the heater resistance and the current required to dissipate the same total power through Joule heating. In this sense, the applied heat source is physically equivalent to electrical excitation, while avoiding the additional complexity associated with coupled electro-thermal simulations. A full 3D electrical (Joule-heating) model could provide further insight into the current distribution and contact effects, especially for high-frequency switching. However, because the heater geometry and material properties are well defined, the thermal response is primarily governed by the total dissipated power, which is accurately captured in our approach. The resistivity of low-stress TiN is assumed to remain constant over

the temperature range considered [30]. This assumption can be relaxed if experimental data show a temperature-dependent resistivity, which typically depends on the quality of the TiN film. In that case, the effective power dissipation can be kept consistent by adjusting the pulse duration or amplitude accordingly. A rise time and a fall time of 10 ns are assumed for the heat pulse. The thermal properties of all materials used in the calculations are summarized in Table 1.

Fig. 1. (a) Cross-sectional schematic of the phase-shifter structure used for the thermal simulations. The widths of the tungsten and copper vias are set to $5\ \mu\text{m}$, with corresponding thicknesses of $0.8\ \mu\text{m}$ and $1.69\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively. A $10\ \text{nm}$ -thick SiO_2 layer is included between the Si core and SiN_x to account for the effects of chemical-mechanical polishing. The thicknesses of the air cladding, buried oxide (BOX), and substrate regions are $5\ \mu\text{m}$, $0.8\ \mu\text{m}$, and $5\ \mu\text{m}$, respectively. (b) Schematic illustrating the placement of the vias used for electrical connection to the constant-width heater.

Table 1. Thermal properties of different materials used in the calculations

Material	Thermal conductivity (W/mK)	Heat capacity (J/kgK)	Density (kg/m ³)
TiN [20]	29	388	5210
AlN	90 [31]	740 [32]	3160 [33]
SiN_x [34]	3	700	3000
GeSe [20]	1.5	329	5520
Si [20]	148	711	2330
SiO_2 [20]	1.38	709	2203
Cu [35]	397	385	8933
W [36]	164	130	19250
Air [35]	0.0263	1006.43	1.17659

Figure 2 shows the temporal evolution of the temperature at six specific locations within the GeSe layer, denoted in the inset. The results indicate that different regions of GeSe reach the

melting temperature at different times. For instance, the melting threshold is crossed at 598 ns for the top-center point, 638 ns for the top-left, 692 ns for the mid-center, 825 ns for the bottom-center, and 836 ns for the mid-left location. This non-uniform heating implies that the phase transition in GeSe does not occur simultaneously across the entire layer; instead, different regions undergo phase change sequentially. Consequently, varying the duration of the heat pulse allows for control over the degree of amorphization. This enables encoding multiple phase-shift levels by simply adjusting the pulse duration at a fixed power, i.e., using pulse width modulation (PWM), which is a simpler approach from a system-driving point of view than pulse amplitude modulation (PAM). This is especially true because of the large driving powers needed for electrical heaters.

Fig. 2. Temporal evolution of the temperature at six specific locations within the GeSe layer.

Subsequently, we calculated the temperature distribution over a mesh grid within the GeSe layer for various pulse durations, using a time step of 1 ns. The resulting temperature profiles from the thermal simulations were then imported into Lumerical FDE for optical mode calculations. Our calculations show that, at mesh points where the temperature exceeds the melting point, the cooling rate from the melting temperature to the glass-transition temperature ranges from 1.46 K/ns to 1.51 K/ns, which is above the cooling rate required for amorphization (1 K/ns) [37]. Local amorphization is therefore assumed at these mesh points [37,38]. The simulation domain for mode analysis, shown in Fig. 3(a), is 2 μm wide and 4 μm thick. The horizontal mesh size was set to 10 nm, whereas the vertical mesh size was non-uniform: 2 nm in the SiO_2 gap and SiN_x , 1 nm in GeSe, 5 nm in AlN and TiN, and 10 nm in the remaining regions. The simulations were carried out at a wavelength of 1.55 μm . The refractive indices of Si and SiO_2 were taken from Palik's data [39]. The refractive indices of SiN_x , TiN, and AlN are taken as 2.0 [40], $3.1477 + 5.8429i$ [39], and $2.018 + 0.00008i$ [41], respectively. For crystalline and amorphous GeSe, the refractive indices are $3.258987 + 0.00104i$ and 3.085431 [11], respectively. The simplified cross-section used for the optical calculations is physically consistent because it yields the same effective indices and field distributions for the fundamental TE mode as those obtained with the cross-section used for the heat simulations. The spatial distributions of the normalized electric-field intensity of the fundamental TE mode in the crystalline and amorphous states of GeSe are shown in Figs. 3(b) and 3(c), respectively. The absorption losses of the fundamental TE mode in the fully crystalline and fully amorphous states are 40 dB/cm and 19.3 dB/cm, respectively. In the fully amorphous state, the loss contribution from GeSe is zero; therefore,

19.3 dB/cm corresponds to the loss induced by the heater alone. This low heater-induced loss arises from the high field confinement achievable in a 300-nm-thick SOI platform. Although placing the heater farther from the Si waveguide would further reduce this loss, it would also degrade both the thermal efficiency and the cooling dynamics. Therefore, the 500 nm heater spacing considered in this paper represents the best trade-off we found between efficient heating and very low optical loss.

Fig. 3. (a) Schematic of the simulation domain for the calculation of optical propagation characteristics; spatial distribution of electric field intensity in (b) crystalline and (c) amorphous states of GeSe.

The phase shift (ϕ) is determined from the change in the effective index of the fundamental TE mode as the amorphization fraction varies. Figure 4(a) shows the phase shift as a function of pulse width. Amorphization begins at approximately 598 ns, and as the pulse duration increases, the amorphous fraction of GeSe—calculated by averaging the permittivity distribution over the mesh grid—also increases, as shown in Fig. 4(b). A phase shift of π is reached for a pulse duration of 824 ns. However, the encoded phase-shift levels are highly non-uniform. This is evident from Fig. 4(c), which shows the difference between adjacent phase-shift levels ($d\phi$) for a 1 ns change in pulse width. At 599 ns, $d\phi$ reaches 0.195π for only a 1 ns increment, indicating abrupt changes in the phase shift. This behavior arises from non-uniform localized amorphization within the GeSe layer combined with uniform power dissipation along the propagation direction, i.e., no variation in the cross-section along that direction. Moreover, Fig. 4(d) shows that the phase-shift variation closely follows the change in the confinement factor (ΔCF) of the GeSe layer relative to its fully crystalline state. Such irregular phase encoding as a function of pulse width can severely degrade the performance of PNNs. Therefore, phase shifters based on this design are unsuitable for finely tuned reconfigurability, for example in high-accuracy PNNs operated under PWM.

Next, we evaluated the phase shift under PAM driving while keeping the pulse duration fixed at 1 μ s. The power was swept from the onset of amorphization to the point at which the GeSe layer becomes fully amorphous, ranging from 6.5 mW/ μ m to 7.5 mW/ μ m in steps of 0.01 mW/ μ m. The resulting encoded phase-shift levels, together with the differences between adjacent levels, are presented in Figs. 5(a) and 5(b). The results show that the phase shift again varies highly non-uniformly, which can be attributed to the irregular amorphization behavior of the GeSe as the heater power increases. In this case, the maximum value of $d\phi$ rises to 0.43π . PAM driving therefore also proves unsuitable for encoding well-spaced phase-shift levels. This result

Fig. 4. Variation of (a) phase shift, (b) amorphous fraction, (c) difference between adjacent phase shift levels ($d\phi$), and (d) the change in confinement factor in GeSe (ΔCF), with the pulse duration for a heater with constant-width along the light propagation direction.

is expected, as PAM and PWM driving schemes are correlated through the total pulse energy delivered to the system.

Fig. 5. Variation of (a) phase shift, and (b) difference between adjacent phase shift levels ($d\phi$), with the pulse power

4. Segmented heater design and phase shift modelling

To achieve well-spaced phase-shift levels, we introduced a segmented heater design with increasing width along the light propagation direction. Increasing the heater width reduces its electrical resistance, thereby decreasing the power dissipation and lowering the local temperature in the GeSe layer. As a result, GeSe segments located beneath heaters of different widths experience different degrees of amorphization. This segmentation approach enables a smoother overall amorphization profile, which is particularly beneficial in the presence of a non-uniform optical

mode profile, because the combined response of the segments is more gradual than that of a phase shifter with a uniform heater width. For a fixed increment in heater width, increasing the number of segments enlarges the difference in power dissipation between the first and last segments, thereby enhancing the temperature contrast across the heater. We selected the number of segments such that near-complete amorphization of the GeSe layer beneath the last heater segments can be achieved while keeping the temperature in the first heater segment below the melting temperature of SiO₂, thereby avoiding melting of the SiO₂ near the TiN heater. For our calculations, we considered 15 heater segments with widths (w) increasing from 1.0 μm to 1.7 μm in steps of 0.05 μm , as shown in Fig. 6. The temperature distribution across the GeSe segments was then calculated.

Fig. 6. Schematic of the segmented heater with increasing width along the light propagation direction.

Figure 7(a) presents the variation of heater power as a function of heater width. The highest power dissipation, 14.5 mW/ μm , occurs for $w = 1.0 \mu\text{m}$, whereas the lowest value, 8.53 mW/ μm , corresponds to $w = 1.7 \mu\text{m}$. The temperature distribution in each GeSe segment is obtained using 2D heat-transfer simulations, with the heater power scaled according to the local TiN width. The effect of thermal gradients at the interfaces between segments is expected to be minimal because the heater is very thin, the width difference between adjacent segments is small, and the rest of the cross-sectional geometry remains unchanged. Furthermore, as in the constant-width heater case, the electrical vias are positioned sufficiently far from the phase-shifter region to avoid influencing the heating and cooling dynamics of the GeSe. Under these conditions, the thermal behavior is predominantly governed by the cross-sectional structure, making the 2D approximation well justified for this scenario. The corresponding electrical inputs can be estimated from the resistivity of TiN and the required power dissipation in each heater segment. For a pulse width of 1 μs , the maximum and minimum temperatures reached in the different GeSe segments are shown in Fig. 7(b). For widths up to 1.65 μm , the minimum temperature remains above the melting threshold, indicating complete amorphization of all these segments, while near-complete amorphization is achieved for the last segment. In addition, Fig. 7(a) shows that the maximum heater temperature (1475 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) remains below the melting point of SiO₂ (1713 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), confirming that nearby SiO₂ does not melt. Furthermore, during full amorphization, the maximum temperatures reached in the first heater segment are 1475 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in AlN, 1429 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in SiN_x, and 1246 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the Si core, all of which remain below their respective melting or stability points (2200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [42], 1700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [43], and 1414 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [44]). This ensures selective melting of GeSe while the surrounding materials remain structurally stable. As shown in Fig. 7(c), increasing the pulse duration enhances the temperature contrast (ΔT) between the GeSe segments relative to the last segment. During progressive amorphization, segments that have already transitioned to the amorphous state retain their phase because the cooling rates are sufficiently high to suppress recrystallization. For a 1 μs pulse, the cooling rates from the melting point to the glass-transition

temperature range from 1.15 K/ns to 1.51 K/ns across the segments. Furthermore, PCM segments can be programmed directly from a fully crystalline state, i.e., without prior amorphization. This enables the configuration to be set in a single step. If reprogramming is required, the device can first be returned to a complete reset state (fully crystalline) before a new programming sequence is applied. Such an initialization step can improve the repeatability and reliability of the programming process. After programming, the device operates without reaching such elevated temperatures, and thus no additional thermal stress or drift is introduced during normal operation. Based on these observations, material instability, interdiffusion, or thermo-optic perturbations are not expected to significantly affect the device performance.

Fig. 7. Variation of (a) heater power and maximum temperatures across TiN, (b) maximum and minimum temperatures across GeSe (T_{max} and T_{min}), and (c) temperature difference (ΔT) across segments relative to the last segment for different pulse durations, with the heater width.

Next, we evaluated the phase shift of the segmented heater based structure by varying the heat-pulse duration (PWM driving). Each segment has a length of $5.7 \mu\text{m}$, giving a total phase-shifter length of $85.5 \mu\text{m}$. The phase-change behavior of GeSe is modeled using the same approach as in the constant-width heater case. The variation of the overall phase shift with pulse duration is shown in Fig. 8(a). Unlike the constant-width configuration, the segmented design exhibits a smooth phase-shift response, as indicated by the small differences between adjacent phase-shift values $d\phi$ in Fig. 8(b), even though the individual segments show highly non-uniform behavior. The maximum $d\phi$ is approximately 0.024π at $\Delta t = 358$ ns, while for most pulse durations it remains very small. This smooth behavior is attributed to the gradual, averaged amorphization across multiple segments, as illustrated in Fig. 8(c), in contrast to the abrupt amorphization observed with a single heater segment. The optical absorption losses in TiN and GeSe are found to vary between 0.34 dB and 0.17 dB with increasing amorphous fraction, as shown on the second y-axis of Fig. 8(c). The total insertion loss, arising from absorption in the heater and GeSe as well as scattering at the interfaces between the Si waveguide and the phase shifter, varies from 0.6 dB to 0.38 dB for phase-shift levels ranging from 0 to π . With this configuration, a phase shift ranging from 0 to π is achieved for pulse durations between 142 ns and 1015 ns. Although the spacing between phase-shift levels is not perfectly uniform, it is sufficiently consistent to map a large number of phase-shift levels between 0 and π to the corresponding pulse widths. The phase-shift variation can be fitted by an error function, shown in Fig. 8(a), with an R^2 value of 0.9987. The fitted function is $y = a \operatorname{erf}(b(x - c)) + d$, where y is the phase shift, x is the pulse duration in microseconds, $a = 8062$, $b = 0.6144$, $c = -4.265$, and $d = -8061$.

Table 2 compares the number of encoded phase-shift levels obtained for different pulse-width resolutions. In each case, the spacing between adjacent phase shifts is required to be no smaller than 0.004π . As can be seen, the number of encoded levels for the variable-width heater is 164, 105, 82, and 60, compared with 36, 21, 17, and 13 for the constant-width heater at pulse-duration resolutions of 0.5 ns, 1 ns, 2 ns, and 5 ns, respectively. Moreover, the range of $d\phi$ is much

Fig. 8. Variation of (a) phase shift (ϕ), (b) difference between adjacent phase shift levels ($d\phi$), and (c) amorphous fraction and absorption loss with the pulse duration for the combined GeSe segments.

smaller in the former case. Therefore, the segmented heater with variable width along the propagation direction provides a significantly smoother phase-shift response under PWM driving than the constant-width heater, with the potential to encode hundreds of well-spaced phase-shift levels. Our phase-change model based on the melt–quench process establishes a direct mapping between pulse duration and the spatial extent of amorphization. Microscopic effects such as nucleation kinetics, stochasticity, and resistance drift are not explicitly captured in the present model. However, the primary objective of this work is to demonstrate a deterministic thermal design framework that enables monotonic and spatially controlled amorphization. The predicted number of levels should therefore be interpreted as an upper bound under idealized conditions. Nevertheless, the model captures the key thermal mechanisms governing amorphization and thus provides a meaningful basis for device design. In the case of partial amorphization, the segment length along the propagation direction can be increased to preserve the required π phase shift, thereby ensuring the robustness of the overall concept.

Table 2. A comparison of encoded phase-shift levels for constant and variable-width architectures

Pulse width resolution (ns)	No. of levels constant-width	No. of levels variable-width	$d\phi$	
			constant-width	variable-width
0.5	36	164	0.004π to 0.098π	0.004π to 0.015π
1	21	105	0.004π to 0.195π	0.004π to 0.026π
2	17	82	0.005π to 0.3π	0.004π to 0.04π
5	13	60	0.005π to 0.398π	0.004π to 0.058π

We also calculated the phase shift for the variable-width heater configuration under PAM driving, using a fixed pulse duration of $1 \mu\text{s}$. The power dissipation in the first heater segment was swept from $6.6 \text{ mW}/\mu\text{m}$, corresponding to the onset of amorphization in the first GeSe segment, to $14.6 \text{ mW}/\mu\text{m}$, corresponding to complete amorphization of the final GeSe segment, in steps of $0.2 \text{ mW}/\mu\text{m}$. The average power dissipation across all segments therefore varies from $5.0 \text{ mW}/\mu\text{m}$ to $11.1 \text{ mW}/\mu\text{m}$. As expected, the phase shift exhibits behavior similar to that observed under PWM driving, namely a smoother phase-shift variation, as illustrated in Figs. 9(a) and 9(b). These results confirm that the segmented heater design provides significantly improved uniformity in phase-shift variation under both PWM and PAM driving. This improved performance makes the segmented design more suitable for integration into Mach–Zehnder interferometers and related PICs, enabling precise reconfigurability of phase shifters, limited mainly by the bit resolution of the digital-to-analog converters (DACs), for applications such as high-accuracy PNNs [45].

Fig. 9. Variation of (a) phase shift, and (b) difference between adjacent phase shift levels ($d\phi$), with the pulse power for the combined GeSe segments.

Table 3 compares the encoded phase-shift levels achieved in this work with those reported in previous studies demonstrating multilevel transmittance or phase shifting using low-loss PCMs and different heating approaches. The number of encoded levels obtained in our work is comparable to, and in some cases higher than, those achieved using doped-semiconductor or PIN-diode heaters.

Table 3. A comparison of encoded levels using low-loss PCMs

Reference	PCM	Heater	No. of Levels	Insertion loss (dB)
[8]	Sb ₂ Se ₃	Doped-silicon	9	Not reported
[24]	Sb ₂ S ₃	Doped-silicon	128	0.6
[25]	Sb ₂ S ₃	PIN diode	8	0.4
[19]	Sb ₂ Se ₃	ITO	84	Not reported
[7]	Sb ₂ S ₃	PIN diode	32	<1.0
[26]	Sb ₂ Se ₃	PIN diode	64	0.36
[9]	Sb ₂ Se ₃	Doped-silicon	10	0.36
This Work	GeSe	TiN	164 (Simulation)	0.6

Our design adheres to typical foundry design rules, with the heater width set to a minimum of 1 μm and increased in steps of 50 nm. The average power dissipation across all segments is 0.94 W and the pulse duration ranges between 142 and 1015 ns, therefore energy dissipation ranges from 133 nJ to 955 nJ, corresponding to different phase-shift levels between the fully crystalline and fully amorphous states of GeSe. Although narrower heaters could further reduce the overall power consumption, the present design is well suited to applications with low reconfiguration rates, where weight programming dominates the total energy budget. Moreover, the proposed segmented-heater approach is general and can be extended to other waveguide platforms and PCM materials, with the potential for lower power consumption under relaxed or alternative design rules. The current design reflects a balance among optical performance, thermal efficiency, and foundry constraints. Although further optimization is possible, it involves inherent trade-offs. For example, reducing the device length by increasing the PCM thickness or enhancing the modal overlap would increase the insertion loss, as noted in our simulations. Similarly, modifying the heater geometry could improve the heating efficiency and cooling dynamics, but would require careful co-optimization of both optical and thermal performance.

5. Conclusions

We investigated a GeSe-integrated silicon-waveguide phase shifter incorporating a TiN heater. Our analysis revealed that non-uniform local heating leads to spatially varying amorphization in GeSe, causing different regions to switch at different pulse durations. As a result, multiple phase-shift levels can be encoded by varying the pulse duration at constant power (PWM driving). However, these levels are highly irregular because of abrupt and non-uniform amorphization. To address this issue, we proposed a segmented heater design with a width that gradually increases along the light propagation direction. This architecture enables smoother overall amorphization across the GeSe segments, producing a more continuous phase-shift response. With this approach, hundreds of well-spaced phase-shift levels between 0 and π can be mapped to different pulse durations, corresponding to a resolution greater than 7 bits. Under PAM driving, both heater designs exhibit trends similar to those observed under PWM driving. This study demonstrates that segmented heaters with variable width provide superior performance compared with uniform heaters, enabling energy-efficient, multilevel, non-volatile phase shifters for next-generation programmable photonic systems, particularly PNNs.

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